

Investigating the mediating effect of work motivation on work engagement

Chin-Yi Shu
Dony Halomoan Siregar
Business Administration Department
Ming Chuan University

Date Submitted : May 5, 2015

Date Accepted : June 10, 2015

ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of differing social environments within a school setting on teachers' work motivation and its impacts on work engagement. Self-determination theory (SDT) defines social environment as an important factor in an individual's motivation and this along with a modified Job Demand-Resource (JD-R) model forms the basis of this investigation into the mediating effect of work motivation on work engagement. A paired questionnaire was distributed to 64 schools in Indonesia. Sixty-four headmasters and 294 teachers took part in the research. Results suggest that some aspects of the social environment within a school can affect teachers' work motivation and their subsequent work engagement (paternalistic leadership and team relationships), whilst others (pupil related inputs) appear to have little impact on work motivation and engagement.

Keywords: *paternalistic leadership, self-determination theory, team member exchange, work engagement*

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a lifelong process of behavioral change and development in which teachers have a key role to play (Kocabas, 2009). Maslach and Leiter (1997) have suggested that for a teacher to be most effective in this role they should be fully engaged, involved and motivated. Schaufeli, Salanova, González-Romá, and Bakker (2002) found that the more involved and engaged teachers are in their work, the more they tend to feel strong and vigorous, enthusiastic and optimistic about the work they do and are very often immersed in that work. Kirkpatrick (2007) has demonstrated that the more people are engaged in their work, the better the outcomes are for both employees and organizations. This suggests that it is important to understand how to get the best out of teachers and what can affect their levels of work motivation

and work engagement.

The Indonesian school system is one of the largest and most diverse in the world (La Rocque, 2015). Primary, junior, and senior education are managed by the districts, with the Ministry of Education and Culture (MOEC) responsible for the overall system, and the Islamic schools are managed by the Ministry of Religious Affairs (MORA). Since the early 1980s, the quality of education remains a significant problem as most Indonesian student's performance are lower than most of the neighboring countries. One of the contributing factors to this is the shortage of experienced teachers (La Rocque, 2015). Thus, understanding the factors that would affect teachers' motivation and engagement is important to help address this issue.

Self-determination theory (SDT; Deci & Ryan, 1985; Ryan & Deci, 2000) provides a theoretical basis for understanding the psychological mechanisms through which an individual's work motivation and engagement may be affected. SDT suggests that there are several factors involved in determining an individual's level of motivation, behavior and well-being. The impact of social environment is one factor among others such as personality development, self-regulation, and the role of universal psychological needs. Most studies have focused on the role played by personality, self-regulation etc. However, the key focus of this study will be the role played by social environment.

It is known that people who are motivated in their tasks intrinsically find inherent rewards in what they are doing. They find the activity enjoyable, satisfying and interesting; therefore, they continue to engage in it simply for the sake of doing that particular activity. Extrinsic motivation on the other hand occurs when individuals carry out a task because they get an instrumental, external reward out of it (Gagné & Deci, 2005; Ryan & Deci, 2000). Regardless of the driving force behind motivation, Atkinson (2000) and Glynn, Aultman and Owens (2005), found out that where teachers have stated that they are satisfied with their contribution towards their students' learning, it is motivation rather than overall professional ability that can play a significant role in student learning.

Motivation acts as an important driver for teachers because it helps them to strive to achieve their targets (Inayatullah & Jehangir, 2012). Work motivation drives teachers to improve their skills and knowledge which in turn influences students' levels of achievement (Mustafa & Othman, 2010). Gagné and Koestner (2002), found that individuals with high levels of intrinsic motivation display significantly higher levels of commitment to their organization and are not as likely to contribute to turnover rates (Richer, Blanchard & Vallerand, 2002) as well as display physical symptoms of stress (Otis & Pelletier, 2005).

As work motivation and engagement appear to have a key role to play in teacher performance it is important to try to understand what may influence these drivers. Demerouti, Bakker,

Nachreiner, and Schaufeli (2001) have suggested that every occupation has its own specific risk factors associated with performance. These factors can be classified into two general categories: job demands and job resources. The Job Demand-Resource (JD-R) model was developed to assess the impact of these factors on burnout and work engagement. Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) adapted the JD-R model to accommodate school environmental factors, in which paternalistic leadership and team member relationships represent job resources and pupil related inputs represent job demands.

Previous research by Hakanen, Bakker, and Schaufeli (2006) investigated the effect of the JD-R model on teachers' work engagement, but did not consider the impact of work motivation on work engagement despite the fact that this is assumed to play an important role in the occupational environment. To address this, the current study investigates factors that influence teachers' work motivation and impact on their work engagement.

Whereas previous research has focused upon the impact of individuals' perception of the work environment, this study aims to focus on the impact of various multilevel factors such as students' and their parents' behavior; relationships with co-workers; the leadership and guidance provided by the principal of the school plus the impact of motivational factors (autonomous motivation), all in a school environment.

Furthermore, building on self-determination theory (Deci & Ryan, 2000), our study proposes and tests a motivational model of intra-individual changes in teacher's work engagement. The model posits that changes in teachers' perceptions of the school environment are likely to predict changes in work engagement through changes in motivational factors.

II. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Self-Determination Theory

Self-determination Theory (SDT) highlights the importance of humans' evolved inner resources for personality development and behavioral self-regulation (Ryan, Kuhl & Deci, 1997). SDT assumes that "human beings are active, growth-oriented organisms who are naturally inclined

toward integration of their psychic elements into a unified sense of self and integration of themselves into larger social structures" (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

SDT distinguishes intrinsic from extrinsic motivation. Intrinsic motivation involves people doing activities for their own sake because they find that particular task to be inherently rewarding and satisfying. Extrinsic motivation, on the other hand, is when people are motivated to do tasks simply because they get an external reward for doing that task. The highest and most ideal form of motivation is intrinsic motivation, wherein a motivation lies at the other end of the spectrum, considered the lowest form of motivation as it occurs when people do not occur any form of motivation at all (Gagne & Deci, 2005).

Teachers contribute to society and may often see teaching as a calling and therefore exhibit high levels of intrinsic motivation (Alexander, 2008; Richardson & Watt, 2006; Scott, Stone & Dinham, 2001). Research has suggested that the professional competence of educators does not play a huge role in students' successful learning as motivational levels do (Atkinson, 2000; Glynn, Aultman & Owens, 2005). Motivation appears to regulate levels of energy; drive to learn; the ability to work effectively and ultimately, to fulfill or actualize a person's potential. It has also proven instrumental in people's interest and sense of enjoyment in their study (Martin, 2003).

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Relationship between School Environmental Factors and Work Motivation

Teaching, including background functions such as administration can be seen as a highly stressful profession (Shu, 2003). Teacher stress is a function of job demands, degree of social support, and job constraints in school (Payne, 1983). One major source of job dissatisfaction and demotivation in employees is job stress (Wani, 2013). Two central characteristics of any workplace environment are job demands and job resources as described in the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Based on this model, one can define job demands as one's tasks on the job that require the

employee to exert much physical or psychological effort, or tasks that demand much physical or psychological costs. On the other hand, job resources help reduce the stress produced by job demands by helping employees attain their work objectives, encourage personal development, and by alleviating negative effects of the physical or psychological costs incurred due to job demands (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007).

Zooming into a school environment specifies examples of job demands and job resources. Examples of job demands include work overload, teachers' problems with their roles, faulty equipment, problems with school policies, conflicts with other faculty members, and of course problems brought about by students' undesirable behaviors (Byrne, 1999; Rudow, 1999). Examples of job resources on the other hand include clear delineations in job roles, positive interpersonal relationships with one's colleagues, and supportive superiors (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). Previous research has proven that employees suffering from job demands that are too heavy and inappropriate lead to decreased energy, eventually resulting in exhaustion and stress (Bakker, Demerouti, Taris, Schaufeli & Schreurs, 2003).

Bakker and Demerouti (2007) have stated that job resources may contribute to employee motivation either as intrinsic or extrinsic sources of motivation. An absence or deficiency of job resources can therefore lead to employee demotivation and dissatisfaction, plus a reduced sense of accomplishment (Bakker, Demerouti, Taris, Schaufeli & Schreurs, 2003).

Once in school, to achieve success, teachers must be able to interact with their headmaster, other teachers, students and their parents as well to produce satisfactory results. This process alone can place a great many demands on an individual. The study focuses on the role of interpersonal factors on work motivation and subsequent work engagement. Factors such as: the interaction between teacher and headmaster; students' disrespectful behavior; problems posed by parental behavior; and the role played by colleagues' support (or lack of it).

For this research students' disrespectful behavior and problems posed by parental behavior

were grouped together and described as 'pupil related inputs'. These data were then combined with 'paternalistic leadership' and 'relationships with colleagues' into an overall grouping called 'school environmental factors'. This grouping formed the basis of our first hypothesis:

Ho1: 'School environmental factors' are related to work motivation.

Relationship between Paternalistic Leadership and Work Motivation

Farh and Cheng (2000) defined paternalistic leadership as 'a style of leadership that combines strong discipline and authority with fatherly benevolence and moral integrity couched in a personality atmosphere'. Paternalistic leadership has three dimensions: benevolence, moral, and authoritarian leadership.

Paternalistic leadership may lead to positive responses from employees as long as this leadership style is freely accepted by both employees and superiors. This may also be a contributing factor to employee motivation. An interaction of the three dimensions is also necessary for this leadership style to succeed in motivating employees (Farh & Cheng, 2000). To be more specific, the authoritarian aspect of the leader contributes to the employees' sense of control and order, and prompts them to obey the leader unquestioningly (Cheng, Chou, Wu, Huang & Farh, 2004). This seemingly rigid approach is tempered by the benevolence dimension which induces feelings of gratitude and reciprocation in employees. Lastly, the leader's sense of morality encourages respect from subordinates.

According to the JD-R model, the relationship in school with the leader or headmaster should represent a job resource providing supporting aspects from leader to subordinates. The leadership model proposed by Cheng, Chou, Wu, Huang, and Farh (2004), describes the authoritarian dimension of paternalistic leadership as demanding and unquestioning response to the leader. This aspect of the model was not considered to be supportive and it was decided to remove any consideration of this aspect of paternalistic leadership from the study. With this exclusion in mind it was proposed that:

Ho1a: Paternalistic leadership is positively related to work motivation

Relationship between Relationships with Colleagues and Work Motivation

Team-Member Exchange (TMX) Theory provides a means of assessing the reciprocity between members of a team. TMX describes the quality of relationships among team members. Seers found that in terms of predicting employee outcomes at work, within-group relationships-also called lateral relationships-proved to be more significant and vital than relationships with superiors (aka vertical relationships). In the present study it was decided that 'relationships with colleagues could be seen as equivalent to reciprocity between team members and can therefore be assessed using TMX theory (Seers, 1989).

For this study it was decided that the variable relationships with colleagues could be considered, equivalent to social support from colleagues, as per the JD-R model and could therefore be seen as a job resource (Martinussen, Richardsen & Burke, 2007) wherein having access to good quality job resources can be intrinsically or extrinsically motivating whilst the lack of it could negatively impact one's motivation (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007). It is therefore proposed that:

Ho1b: TMX is positively related to work motivation.

Relationship between 'Pupil Related Inputs' and Work Motivation

'Pupil related inputs' are defined as problems caused by students' disrespectful behavior and problems posed by parental behavior. Student behavior is one of the most critical concerns in schools today which consists of efforts to satisfy personal needs for: survival; belonging and love; power; freedom; and fun. Friedman (1994) states that it is how the student feels on the inside that produces disrespectful behavior. McFadden, March, Price and Hwang (1992) found that teachers reported encountering a variety of frequent challenging behaviors including multiple occurrences of disrespect, verbal abuse, truancy, tardiness, fighting, harassment and

general classroom disruption. Over time, repeated challenging behaviors can lead to reduced teacher job satisfaction (Borg & Riding, 1991).

Friedman (1995) found that teachers reported disrespect towards them as producing the heaviest impact on levels of self-efficacy and their job satisfaction. Pastor and Erlandson (1982) also observed that there exists a positive relationship between job satisfaction and work motivation. In his study about teacher work motivation and job satisfaction, Thomas (2010) also cemented the idea that the more disrespectful students are towards their teachers, work motivation of the teachers significantly decreases.

Problems posed by parental behavior represent issues that arise from students' parents who either care too much or too little about their educational performance. Either extreme of behavior has been found to play a significant role in teacher stress (Shu, 2003). It has been found out in the previous research that higher levels of stress in the work place can lead to reduced motivation (Wani, 2013). In this study, it is assumed that stress caused by problems posed by parental behavior will affect teachers' work motivation. Therefore it is proposed that:

Ho1c: Pupil related problems are negatively related to work motivation.

Mediating Effect of Work Motivation between School Environmental Factors and Work Engagement

Maslach and Leiter (1997) describe engagement as characterized by energy, involvement, and efficacy. Work engagement has also been defined by Schaufeli and colleagues "as a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind". The three major dimensions of work engagement are the following: vigor, dedication, and absorption.

Vigor is described as high energy levels and mental resilience among employees working together, along with their readiness to continue exerting efforts in the job and persevere in spite of obstacles barring the way. Dedication, the second facet, is represented by employees' feelings that they matter, their sense of enthusiasm about the job, pride, inspiration, and a healthy sense of challenge. This is placed on a higher level

than mere involvement, and is also a step higher than simple identification. Absorption, on the other hand, means being fully absorbed and concentrated in one's work, perhaps even to the point that one does not notice the passage of time and finds it hard to detach oneself from work even after working hours (Schaufeli et al., 2002).

Massie and Douglas (1973), define work motivation as "...that which moves you forward and moves you towards your goal". Gagné and Forest (2008) suggest that the self-determination continuum is useful for predicting optimal functioning in organizations. In their definition the self-determination continuum "...includes employee engagement, job performance subjective well-being, and retention". SDT research has constantly demonstrated that individuals who are engaged in what they are doing also experience greater physical and psychological well-being (Ryan & Deci, 2000). In particular, when one is motivated in his or her job, he or she will be actively engaged with his or her tasks which they find interesting and that, in turn, promote growth (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Using this as a basis it is proposed that:

Ho2: Work motivation is positively related to work engagement.

It is known that optimal functioning in organizations is comprised of employee engagement, job performance, subjective well-being, and retention (Gagné & Forest, 2008). Self-Determination Theory describes the impact of factors such as social environment, self-regulation and universal psychological needs on motivation, behavior and well-being. This research focuses specifically on the impact of school environmental factors within the workplace; how this affects teacher motivation and consequently impacts upon on levels of work engagement. Paternalistic leadership, relationships with colleagues and pupil related problems, represent school environmental factors and can be categorized using the JD-R model as either job resources (paternalistic leadership, relationships with colleagues) or as job demands (pupil related problems). Van den Broeck (2010) proposed, using the JD-R model, that an excess of job demands over job resources may diminish

Figure 1
Research Framework

motivation and decreases one's work engagement, whilst the presence of adequate job resources can lead to enhanced levels of work engagement. Particularly, when school environmental factors are considered as a job resource, this will likely increase one's motivation which triggers an individual to be actively engaged in his/ her work task. In contrast, if school environmental factors are considered as job demands, this will diminish one's motivation which affects an individual's active engagement at work. It is therefore proposed that H3: Work motivation mediates the relationship between school environmental factors and work engagement .

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Measurement Tools

The study identified five variables: paternalistic leadership, pupil related problems, relationship with colleagues, work motivation, and work engagement.

Paternalistic Leadership

The study used a scale developed by Farh, Cheng and Chou (2000), which contains 26 items and uses a six-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree) to record participants' responses. The original measure developed by Cheng et al. (2004) included questions relating to issues of authoritarian leadership. These were deleted for the study because Cheng et al. (2004) stated that authoritarian leadership requires followers to provide unquestioning loyalty to a leader and it is a form of negative leadership (Cheng,

1995) which cannot be considered as a type of job resource. However, with these questions removed and used the Cronbach alpha (internal consistency measure) for Benevolent Leadership, Moral Leadership coefficients of 0.850 and 0.739 respectively were recorded.

Pupil Related Problems

The negative dimension, Disrespect, from Pupil Behavior Patterns (PBP) designed by Friedman (1994) was used to measure student disrespect in the study because disrespect is believed to have the greatest perceived impact on the self-efficacy and job satisfaction of teachers (Hastings & Bahm, 2003). This tool contains eleven statements, using six frequency options ranging from 1 (never) to 6 (always) to measure responses. Statements included: "Students in my class do not treat me with respect"; "Students in my class answer me back", "I demand silence in class and students go on making noise". In the study, the Cronbach alpha internal consistency measure for this tool was 0.872.

Issues relating to problem parents were measured using the sub dimension, achievement press, of Organizational Climate Index (OCI) (Hoy, Smith & Sweetland, 2002). This dimension consisted of five statements that were assessed using four frequency response options ranging from 1 (rarely occurs) to 4 (very frequently occurs). Example statements included: "A few vocal parents can change school policy"; "Parents press for school improvement". In the study the Cronbach alpha internal consistency measure for this tool was 0.700.

Relationships with Colleagues

Seers (1989) developed a tool consisting of 13 statements to measure the TMX construct. Sample items in this tool include: "I frequently provide support and encouragement to other members"; "When other members are busy, I often volunteer to help them out". The response scale for this uses a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). In this research, the Cronbach alpha for this tool was 0.895.

Work Motivation

The study used the Work Extrinsic and Intrinsic Motivation Scale (WEIMS) (Tremblay, Blanchard, Taylor, Pelletier & Villeneuve, 2009). However, the Work Self-Determination Index (W-SDI) proposed by Vallerand (1997) was used to report the results because the study was interested in individuals' displayed motivation level.

The WEIMS scale consists of 18 items. These correspond to the six types of motivation postulated by SDT (i.e., intrinsic motivation, integrated, identified, introjected and external regulations, and amotivation). Participants are asked to indicate their responses on a Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (does not correspond at all) to 7 (corresponds exactly).

From respondents' responses, WEIMS can be used to generate the W-SDI. The formula for determining the W-SDI is as follows: $W-SDI = (+3 \times \text{intrinsic motivation}) + (+2 \times \text{integrated regulation}) + (+1 \times \text{identified regulation}) + (-1 \times \text{introjected regulation}) + (-2 \times \text{external regulation}) + (-3 \times \text{amotivation})$ (Connell & Ryan, 1989). A positive score indicates a self-determined profile and a negative score indicates a non-self-determined profile. Previous research has shown that the self-determination index displays high level of reliability and validity (Pelletier, Dion, Slovic-D'Angelo & Reid, 2004). The Cronbach alpha for the W-SDI in this research was 0.84.

Work Engagement

This questionnaire was answered by the headmaster to understand how they perceive each teacher's work attitude. The Utrecht Work Engagement Scale & Well-Being Survey developed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) was used in the

study to measure teachers' work engagement. The original scale consists of 9 statements but one of them was removed because it was inappropriate for the study approach ("when I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work"). A six-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree) was used to record responses. Statements include: "He/she gets carried away when he/she is working", "He/she feels happy when he/she is working intensely". The Cronbach alpha for this scale in this research was 0.893.

Method Cluster Sampling

The study was conducted in Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia. Based on the 'Education for All Global Monitoring Report' by UNESCO in 2011, Indonesia comes 69th out of 127 countries on the Education Development Index (EDI) (UNESCO, 2011). There are 64 schools participated in the study consisting of 40 state schools, and 24 private schools. The headmaster of each school was contacted and an appointment was made to meet the headmaster in person. After this meeting, each participating headmaster was asked to complete the questionnaire for themselves. Each headmaster then identified five teachers in their school to also complete the questionnaire. Therefore, the sample from each of the 64 schools consisted of one headmaster and five teachers.

Procedures

To ensure that all questions used in the study were fully understandable, two-way translations were performed by bilingual assistants who were proficient in both English and Indonesian dialects. Separate questionnaires were then developed depending upon the type of participant. The headmasters received a questionnaire that included questions about the impact of parent related problems and each teacher's work engagement. Teachers received a questionnaire that included questions about the headmaster's leadership, colleague support and student disrespectful behavior, plus questions relating to their own levels of work motivation.

When using paired questionnaires it is important to guard against bias. Each school has one headmaster that has to choose five teachers

to be assessed because there is a danger that the teacher could tailor their responses in light of being specifically chosen. To avoid this, the teachers remained unaware that they had been specifically chosen by the headmaster and the questionnaires were delivered to them by an independent third party.

Common Method Variance (CMV) suggests that there is a danger when using questionnaire studies that a false internal consistency may occur. Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Podsakoff and Lee (2003) explored four general sources of CMV: (a) the use of a common rater, (b) the manner in which items are presented to respondents, (c) the context in which items on a questionnaire are placed, (d) the contextual influences (time, location and media) used to measure the constructs. In an attempt to prevent CMV in the study, we asked headmasters to answer questions about pupil parent problems to provide an alternative perspective in this area.

There were 64 questionnaires for headmasters and 320 questionnaires for teachers that were directly distributed to the schools by the researcher. Each participant was given three days to complete the questionnaire, and these were then collected, in person, from the headmaster. 100% of questionnaires distributed were returned. All of the questionnaires from headmasters were completed correctly but these were not analyzed in detail. There were 294 analyzed questionnaires from teachers but 26 questionnaires were rejected because of missing data.

Participants

The study focused on headmasters and teachers in state and private schools in Semarang, Central Java, Indonesia. There were 64 headmasters who took part in the study, 51.6% were male and 49.4% were female. There were 46.9% of headmasters had a bachelor degree, 51.6% had a masters' degree, 1.6% of headmasters had alternative qualifications. The average age of the headmasters in the study was 50.58 (SD = 5.248). The youngest headmaster was 32 years old, and the oldest was 60 years old. The average tenure of headmasters was 85.47 months (SD=44.521). The minimum tenure was 6 months and the maximum tenure was 216 months. There were 294 teachers in the study, 61.2% of

the teachers were female and 39.8% were male. Seventy-eight point nine percent had a bachelor degree, 13.6% had a masters' degree, 0.3% had a Ph.D. 7.1% had alternative qualifications. The average of the teachers in the study was 42.94 years old (SD=8.375). The youngest teacher was 23 years old and the oldest was 60 years old. The average tenure of teacher was 216.191 months (SD=109.750), with the minimum tenure was nine months and the maximum tenure was 480 months.

V. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Descriptive Statistical Analysis

The mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and Cronbach's alpha (Churchill, Ford & Walker, 1976; Nunnally, 1978) were used for all the variables of the study shown in Table 1. As suggested by Kline (1998), a skewness above 3.0 and a kurtosis above 10 indicate serious departures from normality in a distribution. All data from variables of the study were as normally distributed in terms of skewness (range from -1.789 to .730) and kurtosis (range from -.644 to 5.906). The alpha coefficient for all variables ranged between 0.609 and .895. Nunnally (1978) suggests that a coefficient alpha greater than 0.7 is acceptable and the majority of variables in the study met this criterion.

Table 1 also shows the range of factor loadings for each variable. The results revealed that the respondents discriminated between the constructs, suggesting convergent validity within the measures, which means that all items are validated to the respective variables.

Discriminant validity concerns the degree to which measures of conceptually distinct constructs differ. In order to test for discriminant validity, a simple factor test was performed on the collected data in the study. A relatively clean solution resulted for the subjective variables, each variable subscale loaded on separate factors. These were used to look at the inter-correlation between items on one variable and questions were eliminated where the style factor absolute value was below 0.50, or between factors lower than 0.30.

The rwg coefficients in Table 2 are averaged

Table 1
Descriptive Analysis

No.	Variable	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	Cronbach Alpha	Factor Loading	Skewness	Kurtosis
Paternalistic Leadership													
1	Benevolence	4.521	.705							.850	.543-.724	-.433	.471
2	Moral	5.100	.815	.311**						.739	.722-.876	-1.789	5.906
Pupil Related Inputs													
3	Student	2.259	.778	.097	-.025					.872	.513-.830	.487	-.313
4	Parent	1.783	.492	-.076	-.094	-.032				.700	.567-.753	.543	-.644
5	TMX	4.014	.448	.342**	.193**	-.094	.064			.895	.531-.751	.340	-.108
6	Work Motivation	9.260	3.609	.280**	.252**	-.193**	.116*	.423**		.609	.396-.749	.730	1.342
7	Work Engagement	5.767	.663	.333**	.386**	-.146*	.013	.448**	.461**	.893	.800-.888	-.427	-.049

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

across groups to evaluate within-group agreement on benevolence leadership, moral leadership, student disrespectful behavior, problem parents, and TMX. The average rwg on these variables are 0.91, 0.86, 0.90, 0.92, and 0.97 respectively, all of them are higher than .70 which means it is acceptable to aggregate the individual level result to group level.

Multilevel Analysis Result

Through Hierarchical Linear Modeling (HLM 7.0, Raudenbush, Bryk & Congdon, 2010), the following aspects of our multilevel mode were tested: (1) the existence of a multilevel structure; (2) the cross-level effect of leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX on work motivation; (3) the cross-level effect of leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX on work engagement; and (4) the mediating effects of work motivation on the

Table 2
r_{wgj} of the group level variables

Variable	Range	Average
Paternalistic Leadership		
Benevolence	0.50 – 0.99	0.91
Moral	0.54 – 1.00	0.86
Pupil Related Inputs		
Student	0.52 – 0.98	0.90
Parent	0.65 – 1.00	0.92
TMX	0.91 – 0.99	0.97

relationship between leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX and work engagement.

The data set contains of two of hierarchically nested levels: 294 teachers (level 1) nested within 64 headmasters (level 2). Work motivation and work engagement were measured at the individual level (level 1), whereas paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX were measured at team level (level 2).

Following research conducted by Raudenbush and Bryk (2002) it was decided to test the existence of a multilevel structure in the model in a preliminary study. Paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and the TMX scores were aggregated to the group mean to empirically justify data aggregation of the employee variables. To explore the degree to which paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX influenced work motivation and work engagement at the individual level, we determined the degree to which individuals' perceptions of paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX were shared within each of the 64 schools (Chan, 1998). To justify the creation of aggregate scores of paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX at the team level, we calculated inter-rater agreement on this measure using the rwg (j) index (James, Demaree & Wolf, 1984). Generally, an rwg greater than 0.7 is desirable, but the higher the value of rwg, the stronger within-group agreement of the construct is reflected (James, Demaree & Wolf, 1984). Table 2 shows the results of the rwg test. Results revealed that all of the dimensions in paternalistic leadership have average rwg 0.91 and 0.86 respectively; Student disrespectful behavior 0.90; problem parents 0.92, and TMX 0.97. All of the rwg scores are greater than .70 suggesting that there is a strong agreement among subordinates within teams (James, 1982).

In this study, the intra-class correlation values (ICC) was also examined to reflect the inter-rater reliability score (Bliese, 2000). The ICC score for work engagement was found to be 0.647. This is greater than the 0.20 as recommended by Bliese. This suggests that strong units in the same group resemble each other. From the score of rwg and ICC, it can be seen that all scores are greater than acceptable levels which suggests that the creation of an aggregation analysis for analyzing the cross-

level is justified.

Hypothesis Testing

In testing the hypotheses, we made a set of multilevel models was made based on the theoretical predictions using the incremental improvement procedure demonstrated by Hox (2010). All scores in the model are shown in the Table 3. These are estimations of fixed effects with robust standard errors. The first model for analysis was the intercept-only model with work engagement as the dependent variable (Model 1).

To test the cross-level of paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX as independent variables to work motivation as mediator, we added paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX to model 2 (see table 3). Results revealed that paternalistic leadership has significant effect on work motivation (Model 2: $\bar{x}_{01} = 1.581$, SE = .66, $p < .05$). However, pupil related inputs appear to have no significant effect on work motivation (Model 2: $\bar{x}_{02} = .033$, SE = .40, $p > .05$). TMX appears to have a significant effect on work motivation (Model 2: $\bar{x}_{03} = 2.955$, SE = 1.02, $p < .01$). Hypotheses 1a, 1c can therefore be accepted and hypotheses 1b can be rejected.

The work motivation variable was added to Model 3 (see Table 3) to test the relationship between work motivation as mediator to work engagement as dependent variable. The coefficients of corresponding parameters estimated in the model was also examined. It would appear that work motivation has a significant effect on work engagement (Model 3: $\bar{x}_{10} = .023$, SE = .01, $p < .05$). As a result of these findings it is possible to accept hypothesis 2.

Entries corresponding to the predicting variables are estimations of the fixed effects. The variables paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX were added to model 4 (see Table 3). To test this hypothesis, the coefficients of corresponding parameters estimated in the model was examined to test the cross-level of paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX as independent variables with work engagement as dependent variable. Paternalistic leadership was found to have a significant effect on work motivation (Model 4: $\bar{x}_{01} = .433$, SE = .15,

Table 3
Multilevel Analysis Result

Variable	Model 1 Null Model	Model 2 X-Me	Model 3 Me-Y	Model 4 X-Y	Model 5 XMe-Y
Level 1					
Intercept (³ ₀₀)	5.030***	-12.826	5.030***	1.067	1.07
Level 2					
Paternalistic Leadership (³ ₀₁)		1.581*		.433**	.462**
Pupil Related Inputs (³ ₀₂)		.033		-0.279	-.315*
TMX (³ ₀₃)		2.955**		.538***	.534***
Mediating Effect					
Work Motivation (³ ₁₀)			.023*		.022*
Model Deviance		1439.738	366.332	354.859	343.761

Source: Present Study

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, and *** $p < .001$

$p < .01$). However, Pupil related inputs appears to have no significant effect on work motivation (Model 4: $x-x_{02} = -.279$, $SE = .14$, $p > .05$). TMX appears to have a significant effect on work motivation (Model 4: $x-x_{03} = .538$, $SE = .14$, $p < .001$). Based on these finding scores, we accept hypotheses 3a, 3b and reject 3c.

Work motivation as a mediator in the relationship between independent variables (paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and TMX) and work engagement as a dependent variable was tested. From the results, it can be seen that the variables in level 2 change when work motivation is included as a mediator. Paternalistic leadership has increased, from Model 4: $x-y_{01} = .433$ to Model 5: $x-y_{01} = .462$, as has the effect of pupil related inputs from Model 4: $x-y_{02} = -.279$ to Model 5: $x-y_{02} = -.315$. However, the value of TMX has decreased from Model 4: $x-y_{03} = .538$ to Model 5: $x-y_{03} = .534$.

VI. CONCLUSION AND CONTRIBUTION

In the research, it has been found that work motivation appears to partially mediate in the causal relationship between school environmental factors and work engagement except in the area of pupil related inputs. Within the framework of the JD-R model, paternalistic leadership and TMX are viewed as a job resource which provides

support and increases motivation. The study shows that even if the teachers have low quality support from supervisor and colleague, high levels of work motivation will pull the level of the work engagement higher as well. This finding is also supported by previous research conducted by Schaufeli and Bakker (2004) which found out that job resources foster work motivation and promote adaptive work behavior, such as work engagement.

The results indicated that there is a significant relationship between paternalistic leadership, TMX and work engagement. There is no significant relationship between pupil related inputs and work engagement. Results further revealed that TMX has the highest degree in affecting teachers' work engagement. As friends in school, other teachers are supporting each other no matter how difficult the condition of headmasters' leadership style, students in the class, and pupils' parents are. This finding is also supported by previous research conducted by Liao, Yang, Wang, Drown and Shi (2013) which also found there was positive relationship between TMX and work engagement.

The findings showed that there is a significant relationship between paternalistic leadership, TMX, and work motivation. According to JD-R model, pupil related inputs is one of the examples of job demand, and it was found out that there

was no significant relationship between pupil related inputs and work motivation. The study has the same research findings conducted by Farh and Cheng's (2000) that benevolence and morality would contribute to work motivation. Furthermore, the study is also similar to the findings of Van Yperen and Hagedoorn (2003), which was found that there was no evidence of a relationship between job demands and intrinsic motivation. Moreover in the study, it was found out that TMX has the highest significant level compared to others. It shows that the relation between teachers has the most important role in affecting work motivation. Teacher can freely talk about their feelings to their colleagues which may decrease stress in work place, and also they can motivate each other because between teachers they have same feelings and experiences as a teacher.

The study has proven that work motivation is significantly related to work engagement. It showed that if a teacher has high level of work motivation, he or she will also have high levels of work engagement. In doing something, someone must be motivated, and if the level of the motivation is high, work engagement is going to be high as well, which in this case is doing teachers' duties.

The study is different from other researches because other studies on this topic usually use one or two predictors for mediator or to dependent variable, but in the study there were more than one predictors used. Other researchers used all the dimensions of paternalistic leadership. Furthermore, the study analyzed two levels: team and individual level, which make this research different from previous research.

Theoretical Contributions

Theoretically, the study addressed a need for researchers to know what affects teachers' work motivation and work engagement the most. In the study, paternalistic leadership, pupil related inputs, and relationship with colleagues were adopted from JD-R model that can make Self-determination Theory for motivation become more complete and clear. Since findings revealed the role of work motivation as a mediator, it gave a contribution that work motivation can

provide additional support to the growing body of empirical literature on teaching.

Practical Contribution

The result of the study showed that high levels of work motivation will lead to high levels of work engagement. To achieve high levels of work motivation that may lead to high levels of work engagement, a teacher must have a good quality of relationship with other teachers, because other teachers face almost the same problem such as students and students' parents or maybe with the headmaster, so there is an empowering interaction between teachers which may lead to stronger personality to cope with problems in the work place.

Teachers also needs supports from their headmasters to be motivated and keep in track as a good teacher under the leadership of the headmaster, because though students in class change overtime as their parents do, but the teachers' relationship with colleagues and support from headmaster will remain needed. As a headmaster, having a supportive leadership style such as paternalistic leadership is really important, because the headmaster can play the role of a father or mother that nurtures and cares for teachers, which can boost the latter's motivation levels thereby increasing the level of work engagement. If the teachers have high level of motivation and engagement, automatically they can perform well in the class that may lead to good student's achievement.

Research Limitation and Further Suggestions

In the study, the used questionnaires were paired to subordinates and supervisors. Though respondents did not remember the name of the questionnaire, the research topic however, involves many sensitive issues regarding their supervisor. In the study, when the respondent had questions, they can ask the researchers' guidance and instructions because we attached the researchers' phone number and email address so we can explain in detail the purpose of the study or any questions regarding the study. In collecting the data, the questionnaires were also contained in sealed bags in order to reduce problems. Due to the sensitivity of the study topic, respondents

might have not answered the questions truthfully.

Based on JD-R model, it can be suggested for future research to examine work overload, role problems, school policies and climate, deficient equipment, and interpersonal conflicts from a job demand perspective. From the job resource perspective, flexible schedules, decision latitude, skill utilization, participation in decision-making, recognition, professional development, and coaching should be investigated.

Originality Index:	91 %
Similarity Index:	9 %
Paper ID:	665871856
Grammarly:	Checked

REFERENCES

- Alexander, P. A. (2008). Charting the course for the teaching profession: The energizing and sustaining role of motivational forces. *Learning and Instruction*, 18(5), 483-491.
- Atkinson, E. S. (2000). An investigation into the relationship between teacher motivation and pupil motivation. *Educational Psychology*, 20(1), 45-57.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The job demands-resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309-328.
- Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E., Taris, T. W., Schaufeli, W. B., & Schreurs, P. J. (2003). A multigroup analysis of the job demands-resources model in four home care organizations. *International Journal of Stress Management*, 10(1), 16-38.
- Bliese, P. D. (2000). Within-group agreement, non-independence, and reliability: Implications for data aggregation and analysis. In K. J. Klein & S. W. Kozlowski (Eds). *Multilevel theory, research, and methods in organizations: Foundations, extensions, and new directions* (pp. 349-381). San Francisco, CA, US: Jossey-Bass
- Borg, M. G., & Riding, R. J. (1991). Towards a model for the determinants of occupational stress among schoolteachers. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 6(4), 355-373.
- Byrne, B. M. (1999). The nomological network of teacher burnout: A literature review and empirically validated model. In R. Vandenberghe & M. A. Huberman (Eds). *Understanding and preventing teacher burnout: A sourcebook of international research and practice* (pp. 15-37). New York, NY, US: Cambridge University Press
- Chan, D. (1998). Functional relations among constructs in the same content domain at different levels of analysis: A typology of composition models. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83(2), 234.
- Cheng, B. S. (1995). Paternalistic authority and leadership: A case study of a Taiwanese CEO. *Bulletin of the Institute of Ethnology Academic Sinica*, 79(3), 119-173.
- Cheng, B. S., Chou, L. F., Wu, T. Y., Huang, M. P., & Farh, J. L. (2004). Paternalistic leadership and subordinate responses: Establishing a leadership model in Chinese organizations. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 7(1), 89-117.
- Churchill Jr, G. A., Ford, N. M., & Walker Jr, O. C. (1976). Organizational climate and job satisfaction in the salesforce. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 13(4), 323-332.
- Deci, E. L., Connell, J. P., & Ryan, R. M. (1989). Self-determination in a work organization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(4), 580.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). The general causality orientations scale: Self-determination in personality. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 19(2), 109-134.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2002). *Handbook of self-determination research*. NY, USA: University Rochester Press.
- Demerouti, E., Bakker, A. B., Nachreiner, F., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2001). The job demands-resources model of burnout. *Journal of*

- Applied Psychology*, 86(3), 499.
- Farh, J. L., & Cheng, B. S. (2000). A cultural analysis of paternalistic leadership in Chinese organizations. In J. T. Li, A. S. Tsui & E. Weldon (Eds.), *Management and organizations in the Chinese context* (pp. 84-127). London, UK: Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Farh, L. J., Cheng, B. S., & Chou, L. F. (2000). A triad model of paternalistic leadership: Constructs and measurement. *Indigenous Psychological Research in Chinese Societies*, 14(1), 3-64.
- Friedman, I. A. (1994). Conceptualizing and measuring teacher-perceived student behaviors: Disrespect, sociability, and attentiveness. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 54(4), 949-958.
- Friedman, I. A. (1995). Student behavior patterns contributing to teacher burnout. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 88(5), 281-289.
- Gagné, M., & Deci, E. L. (2005). Self-determination theory and work motivation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 26(4), 331-362.
- Gagné, M., & Forest, J. (2008). The study of compensation systems through the lens of self-determination theory: Reconciling 35 years of debate. *Canadian Psychology*, 49(3) 225-232
- Gagné, M., & Koestner, R. (2002). Self-determination theory as a framework for understanding organizational commitment. *Society for Industrial and Organizational Psychology, Toronto, Canada*.
- Glynn, S. M., Aultman, L. P., & Owens, A. M. (2005). Motivation to learn in general education programs. *The Journal of General Education*, 54(2), 150-170.
- Hakanen, J. J., Bakker, A. B., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2006). Burnout and work engagement among teachers. *Journal of School Psychology*, 43(6), 495-513.
- Hastings, R. P., & Bham, M. S. (2003). The relationship between student behaviour patterns and teacher burnout. *School Psychology International*, 24(1), 115-127.
- Hox, J. J., Moerbeek, M., & van de Schoot, R. (2010). *Multilevel analysis: Techniques and applications*. NY, USA: Routledge.
- Hoy, W. K., Smith, P. A., & Sweetland, S. R. (2002). The development of the organizational climate index for high schools: Its measure and relationship to faculty trust. *The High School Journal*, 86(2), 38-49.
- Inayatullah, A., & Jehangir, P. (2012). Teacher's job performance: The role of motivation. *Abasyn Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(2), 78-99.
- James, L. R. (1982). Aggregation bias in estimates of perceptual agreement. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 67(2), 219.
- James, L. R., Demaree, R. G., & Wolf, G. (1984). Estimating within-group interrater reliability with and without response bias. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 69(1), 85.
- Kirkpatrick, A. (2007). *World Englishes paperback with audio CD: Implications for international communication and english language teaching*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- Kline, R. B. (1998). Principles and practice of structural equation modeling.
- Kocabas, I. (2009). The effects of sources of motivation on teachers' motivation levels. *Education*, 129(4), 724.
- La Rocque, N. (2015). *Summary of Indonesia's education sector assessment*. Jakarta, Indonesia: ADB Resident Mission
- Liao, F. Y., Yang, L. Q., Wang, M., Drown, D., & Shi, J. (2013). Team member exchange and work engagement: Does personality make a difference? *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 28(1), 63-77.
- Martin, A. J. (2003). The Student Motivation Scale: Further testing of an instrument that measures school students' motivation. *Australian Journal of Education*, 47(1), 88-106.
- Martinussen, M., Richardsen, A. M., & Burke, R. J. (2007). Job demands, job resources, and burnout among police officers. *Journal of Criminal Justice*, 35(3), 239-249.
- Maslach, C., & Leiter, M. P. (1997). *The truth about burnout*. San Francisco, USA: Jossey Bass.
- Massie, J. L., & Douglas, J. (1985). *Managing, a contemporary introduction*. New Jersey, USA: Prentice-Hall.
- McFadden, A. C., Marsh, G. E., Price, B. J., & Hwang, Y. (1992). A study of race and gender bias in the punishment of school

- children. *Education and Treatment of Children*, 15(2), 140-146.
- Mustafa, M., & Othman, N. (2010). The effect of work motivation on teacher's work performance in pekanbaru senior high schools, Riau Province, Indonesia. *SOSIOHUMANIKA*, 3(2), 259-272.
- Nunnally, J. (1978). *Psychometric Theory* (2nd ed.), New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Otis, N., & Pelletier, L. G. (2005). A Motivational Model of Daily Hassles, physical symptoms, and future work intentions among police officers. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 35(10), 2193-2214.
- Pastor, M. C., & Erlandson, D. A. (1982). A study of higher order need strength and job satisfaction in secondary public school teachers. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 20(2), 172-183.
- Payne, R., & Fletcher, B. C. (1983). Job demands, supports, and constraints as predictors of psychological strain among schoolteachers. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 22(2), 136-147.
- Pelletier, L. G., Dion, S. C., Slovinec-D'Angelo, M., & Reid, R. (2004). Why do you regulate what you eat? Relationships between forms of regulation, eating behaviors, sustained dietary behavior change, and psychological adjustment. *Motivation and Emotion*, 28(3), 245-277.
- Podsakoff, P. M., MacKenzie, S. B., Lee, J. Y., & Podsakoff, N. P. (2003). Common method biases in behavioral research: a critical review of the literature and recommended remedies. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 88(5), 879.
- Raudenbush, S. W., & Bryk, A. S. (2002). *Hierarchical linear models: Applications and data analysis methods* (2nd ed.). LA, USA: Sage Publications Inc.
- Raudenbush, S. W., Bryk, A. S., Cheong, Y. F., Congdon, R. T., & du Toit, M. (2006). *HLM 6: Hierarchical linear and nonlinear modeling*. Lincolnwood, IL: Scientific Software International, Inc
- Raudenbush, S. W., Bryk, A. S., & Congdon, R. T. (2010). *Hierarchical linear modeling with the HLM7 programs*. Chicago, USA: Scientific Software International.
- Richardson, P. W., & Watt†, H. M. (2006). Who chooses teaching and why? Profiling characteristics and motivations across three Australian universities. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Teacher Education*, 34(1), 27-56.
- Richer, S. F., Blanchard, C., & Vallerand, R. J. (2002). A motivational model of work turnover. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(10), 2089-2113.
- Rudow, B. (1999). Stress and burnout in the teaching profession: European studies, issues, and research perspectives. In A. M. Huberman (Ed.), *Understanding and preventing teacher burnout: A sourcebook of international research and practice* (pp. 38 – 58). New York, USA: Cambridge University Press.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2006). Self-regulation and the problem of human autonomy: does psychology need choice, self-determination, and will? *Journal of Personality*, 74(6), 1557-1586.
- Ryan, R. M., Kuhl, J., & Deci, E. L. (1997). Nature and autonomy: An organizational view of social and neurobiological aspects of self-regulation in behavior and development. *Development and Psychopathology*, 9(04), 701-728.
- Schaufeli, W. B., Salanova, M., González-Romá, V., & Bakker, A. B. (2002). The measurement of engagement and burnout: A two sample confirmatory factor analytic approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3(1), 71-92.
- Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2004). Job demands, job resources, and their relationship with burnout and engagement: A multi-sample study. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 25(3), 293-315.
- Scott, C., Stone, B., & Dinham, S. (2001). I love teaching but.... International patterns of teacher discontent. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 9(28), 1-7
- Seers, A. (1989). Team-member exchange quality: A new construct for role-making research. *Organizational behavior and human decision processes*, 43(1), 118-135.
- Shu, C. Y. (2003). *Stress in tutor-teachers in Taiwan: exploration and an evaluation of a stress*

- management programme* (Doctoral of Philosophy in Education Dissertation, University of Surrey). Retrieved from <http://uk.bl.ethos.274343>
- Thomas, K. A. (2010). Work motivation and job satisfaction of teachers. *Southeastern Teacher Educational Journal*, 3(1), 101-122.
- UNESCO (2010). *Education for all global monitoring report: Reaching the marginalized*. Oxford, United Kingdom: Oxford University Press. Retrieved from <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/imagvves/0018/001866/186606E.pdf>
- Van den Broeck, A. (2010). *Work motivation. A perspective from the Job Demands-Resources Model and the Self-Determination Theory*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Leuven, Flanders Belgium. Retrieved from <https://anjavandenbroeck.files.wordpress.com/2012/10/doctoral-dissertation-anja-van-den-broeck4.pdf>
- Van Yperen, N. W., & Hagedoorn, M. (2003). Do high job demands increase intrinsic motivation or fatigue or both? The role of job control and job social support. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46(3), 339-348.
- Wani, S. K. (2013). Job stress and its impact on employee motivation: a study of a select commercial bank. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 2(3), 13-18.